

WELCOME to the PREreview + **[Collaborating Partner]**

Live-Review

WHAT

[PREreview](#) and **[Collaborating Partner]** are joining forces to bring together scientists from across the globe for a virtual discussion and collaborative review of recent preprints.

If you want to learn more about Live Reviews, you can check out [this page](#).

WHEN

[DATE]

PREPRINT

Title:

DOI:

Authors (*present today*):

CALL FACILITATORS

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AUTHORS: *[Are the authors present? If so, ask them to identify themselves by adding the word authors to their Zoom name - Go to the upper right-hand corner of the zoom window, and select “Rename”. Authors can be asked to share any questions or particular areas they wish to get feedback on, but otherwise are asked to remain silent until the last ten minutes of the call.]*

EXPERT (Optional):

[A researcher in the field of the preprint topic who has agreed to lead the conversation. The expert is expected to introduce the preprint at the beginning of the discussion. Slides are optional. If there are slides, facilitators need to ensure beforehand that the sharing tool works properly. We recommend inviting the expert to join the call 5-10 minutes before the starting time to test equipment and review the call’s format]

ROLL CALL (optional)

Name | preferred pronouns | location | *participation choice (Listener, Discussion Participant, Review Author)

**Please review the section [OPTIONS TO PARTICIPATE IN THIS LIVE REVIEW](#) before you add your preferred participation choice. If you don’t know yet, that’s okay, you can change it later.*

- *E.g., Daniela Saderi | she/her | Portland, OR, United States | (3) Review Author*
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ABOUT THIS CALL

- The call lasts **90 minutes** and **is recorded via Zoom (video and audio)**.
- Live-caption services are available via **Zoom, which** will also record a **transcript of the call**.
- 📺 Video, 🎧 audio, and 📄 transcript will be shared only with the [NAME OF ORGANIZING ORG] and used to help compose the final review.
- ⚠️👤 **Third-party recordings are strictly prohibited**
- ⚠️👤 **The use of AI notetaking bots, AI Chatbots whether for generating or refining answers, is not permitted during this call.** This is for two main reasons:
 - Using AI goes against the collaborative spirit of our Live Reviews
 - At this note-taking stage of the review process, refining language is not important. If writing in English is a barrier, please feel free to write your comments in your native language and we'll do our best to translate them.
- 🗨️ This **collaborative note-taking document is shared in *editing mode* with all live review participants** who are invited to take notes during the call when prompted. After the call this document will continue to be shared with participants in *suggesting mode* to track changes made after the live review.
- 🎯 The **GOAL** of the Live Review is to **aggregate comments from this discussion into a review** that will then be published on <https://prereview.org> within two weeks from today.

PARTICIPATION GUIDELINES

- ➔ By remaining on this call you agree to abide by the **PREreview Code of Conduct**. We expect everyone to:
 - Use welcoming and inclusive language;
 - Respect differing viewpoints and experiences;
 - Provide feedback that is constructive, *i.e.*, useful to the receiver;
 - Gracefully accept constructive criticism;
 - Show empathy towards other participants and community members.
- 🙋 Please report abusive, harassing, or otherwise, unacceptable behavior by:
 - Direct messaging one of the facilitators on Zoom and asking for immediate help. The facilitators reserve the right to remove participants who exhibit inappropriate or disruptive behavior.
 - Emailing the PREreview team at report@prereview.org explaining the incident, or submitting a claim by filling out this [report form](#) with the option of remaining anonymous.
- 🚫 Please **silence your mic** unless speaking to minimize background noise.
- 🙋 To **ask a question** or contribute to the discussion with your voice, please raise your Zoom hand 🙋 (you'll find it under reactions) or type your question in the Zoom chat.
- To **contribute to the live review discussion** and get the option to be listed as a Discussion Participant or as a Review Author (see options below), you can:
 - 📄 Directly type into this document by typing under the prompted questions below
 - 💬 Type into the Zoom chat - facilitators will paste your answers into this document
 - 🗣️ Voice your thoughts by Raising your hand and unmuting when prompted - facilitators will take notes in this document

OPTIONS TO PARTICIPATE IN THIS LIVE REVIEW

Everyone is welcome to join the Live Reviews and participate in the way they prefer. Please read through the following options on how to participate and ADD YOUR PARTICIPATION CHOICE TO THE [ROLL CALL](#).

Participation Choice	What to expect What to do
<p>1 LISTENER - You choose to “sit in” and don’t contribute to the review discussion in any way</p>	<p>Expect: NO options to be named in the review narrative or be listed as a review author</p> <p>Do: No action required</p>
<p>2 DISCUSSION PARTICIPANT - You choose to contribute to the live review discussion, but you don’t plan to help compile the notes into the final review report</p>	<p>Expect: Option to be named in the review narrative and acknowledged for your contribution to the discussion</p> <p>NO option to be listed as a review author</p> <p>Do: To have your name listed, please add your name and indicate this option style to the Roll Call; Declare Competing Interests (question 21 below)</p>
<p>3 REVIEW AUTHOR - You choose to contribute to the live review discussion AND to volunteer extra asynchronous time (no more than 2 hours total) to compile the notes into the final review report</p>	<p>Expect: Option to be listed as a review author of the final review report that will be published on PRereview.org</p> <p>Do: Please add your name and indicate this option style to the Roll Call and send a direct message to Grace on Zoom with your email address so that we contact you with follow up instructions (also option to email us at community@prereview.org); Declare Competing Interests (question 21 below)</p>
<p>4 PREPRINT AUTHOR - You are an author of the preprint who chose to be here today</p>	<p>Expect: Constructive feedback, direct questions</p> <p>Do: Add “author” to your Zoom name; introduce yourself when prompted by facilitators; do not contribute to the review</p>

PREreview of “State Anxiety Biomarker Discovery: Electrooculography and Electrodermal Activity in Stress Monitoring”

3 Review Authors

by [Daniela Saderi](#) of the [JMIR Publications](#)

Published January 31, 2025 DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14783228](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14783228) License [CC BY 4.0](#)

2 Discussion participants

This review is the result of a virtual, collaborative live review discussion organized and hosted by PREreview and JMIR Publications on January 16, 2025. The discussion was joined by 16 people: 2 facilitators, 1 member of the JMIR Publications team, and 13 live review participants including 3 who agreed to be named but have not contributed to composing this review into its final form: Uday Kumar Chalwadi, Killivalavan Solai, Prasakthi Venkatesan. The authors of this review have dedicated additional asynchronous time over the course of two weeks to help compose this final report using the notes from the Live Review. We thank all participants who contributed to the discussion and made it possible for us to provide feedback on this preprint.

Screenshot of a [review](#) published on [PREreview.org](#) after a Live Review showing how names of participants who choose option 2 and option 3 are displayed.

GROUP DISCUSSION ORIENTATION + (5 minutes)

Let's get started with the discussion! Remember to **keep your feedback clear, constructive, and actionable.**

We will go through **[INSERT TOTAL NUMBER OF QUESTIONS]** with the goal to then assembling a final review. We aim for it to have a structure that follows this schematic representation:

Figure from the [Open Reviewers Reviewer Guide](#) and modified [PLOS Peer Review Template: A quick guide for new peer reviewers](#)

Questions in **bold** are the ones we will read and answer together during this call. The other questions are optional and you may choose to answer them later or leave them blank.

Any questions from participants before we start? Feel free to use the Zoom chat box.

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AUTHOR’S AND/OR EXPERT(S) BRIEF INTRO TO THE WORK AND SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

(5 minutes)

Name:

We ask that the author(s) identify themselves by adding the word “author” to their Zoom name.

After a brief introduction of themselves and the work (optional), the authors are invited to remain silent unless asked a direct question until the last 10 minutes of the call when they’ll be invited to share any remarks they may have.

SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH AND OVERALL IMPRESSION

(15 minutes)

1. What is/are the research question(s) the study attempts to answer? What's the main goal? Why is it important? 🖋️ + 🎤

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2. What is the main approach? What did the authors do to address the research question(s)? 🖋️ + 🎤

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3. What is/are the main finding(s)? 🖋️ + 🎤

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4. What did you find most interesting about the research? (optional)

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5. How does the manuscript relate to published literature on this topic? How would the results lead to future research? (optional)

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6. What is one main strength and one main weakness? (optional)

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EVIDENCE AND EXAMPLES

For this entire section, optionally add an “M” for major issues or an “m” for minor issues at the end of your answer.

Major issue (M): A concern that if remained unaddressed it would compromise the credibility, interpretation and soundness of the study.

Minor issue (m): A concern that left unaddressed would not compromise the credibility, interpretation and soundness of the study.

METHODS / DATA (15 minutes)

7. Are there any issues with the techniques/analyses that the researchers adopt to test the research question? Are these approaches appropriate to best address the

research question? Are suitable controls in place? Were the data interpreted accurately? 🖋️ + 🎤

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***Note for facilitators:** Now discuss possible suggestions for each issue

8. Is sufficient detail provided to allow the reproduction and validation of the study?

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9. Does the study conform to ethical guidelines? 🖋️ + 🎤

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10. Does the manuscript include new data? Are the data used in the manuscript openly available? If so, paste the link. (optional)

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11. *Is the source code for the analyses openly available? If so, paste the link. (optional)*

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LET'S TAKE A 5-MIN BREAK

FIGURES / TABLES & RESULTS

(10 minutes)

12. *Write here any specific comment/note about figures/tables (this could be related to the way data are displayed and your ability to understand the results just by looking at the figures/tables including legends, axis labels, and visualization type).*

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***Note for facilitators:** *Now discuss possible suggestions for each issue*

13. Does the manuscript text support the data shown in the figures/tables? PLOS reminds us, “Do not just take the figures and tables at face value.” (optional)

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14. Are the conclusions supported by the data or do they overreach and need to be nuanced? 🖋️ + 🎤

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***Note for facilitators:** Now discuss possible suggestions for each issue

15. Are limitations to the approach appropriately discussed? Are there limitations that are not discussed? 🖋️ + 🎤

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16. Have the authors adequately discussed ethical concerns? (optional)

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OTHER POINTS

FINAL REMARKS ABOUT THE MANUSCRIPT (5 minutes)

17. Write here any additional comments you might have (this includes overall suggestions on how to improve the readability of the manuscript). 🙌 + 🎤

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18. Would you recommend this manuscript to others to read? (optional)

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19. Would you recommend this manuscript for journal publication? (optional)

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20. What one thing from this work have you learned and may bring into your own practice? (optional)

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21. Use this space to declare any competing interests* - for example you are or have been a collaborator of one of the authors of this manuscript, or you are a direct competitor of the research laboratory conducting the study in this manuscript

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*At PREreview we ask all contributors to disclose any competing interest (CI) that may exist between a review author (or affiliated organization) and the author(s) (or affiliated organization) of the reviewed preprint.

We define a competing interest as anything that interferes with or could reasonably be perceived as interfering with, the objective of a review of a preprint on PREreview. Read more [here](#).

WHAT HAPPENS NEXT?

If you want to help us put together a **final review** that will be published on PREreview and help guide journal peer review of this manuscript, **please email us at [ORGANISER'S EMAIL] or DM us your email address now** and we will reach out to you in the next day or two with instructions on how to contribute.

So that we can credit you with your work on the final review, we ask that all review authors also create an account at PREreview.org which can be done in seconds with your ORCID iD.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION!

FEEDBACK ON THIS CALL

We hope you had a good experience. Please take a few minutes to give us feedback on this event so that we can do better next time.

[ADD LINK TO A FEEDBACK FORM IF YOU HAVE ONE]

STAY IN TOUCH

To learn more about events such as these and PREreview in general you can follow us on [Mastodon](#), [Bluesky](#), and [LinkedIn](#), and keep up with all the latest news by [subscribing to our newsletter](#).

Join our Slack channel: <https://bit.ly/PREreview-Slack>

RESOURCES

- Open Reviewers Toolkit - published on Zenodo under CC BY 4.0
 - [Bias Reflection Guide](#)
 - [Reviewer Guide](#)
 - [Review Assessment Rubric](#)
- On the [PREreview](#) resource page, you will find resources to
 - learn more about our project
 - how to write a review
 - start a preprint journal club
- On the [PLOS Reviewer Center](#) with resources on [how to write a constructive review](#) and much more.
- *[Please share more resources you know of here]*